

To escape the middle-income trap, Vietnam needs a new development model.

Quoc Hai Monday, January 26, 2026 - 08:24

Listen to the audio 2:38

Economist Huynh Thanh Dien believes that Vietnam has not yet fallen into the middle-income trap because it has not reached the threshold. However, if it continues with its current model, the likelihood of falling into the same trajectory as Thailand and the Philippines is very high.

RELATED NEWS

- VinaCapital: Deposit interest rates could approach 7% in 2026.

The period 2026-2030 is considered a "strategic window" for Vietnam to break through to the group of countries with modern industries and avoid falling into the middle-income trap.

Speaking with TheLEADER, Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien, an economic expert, emphasized that the new growth driver does not lie in the slogan "technology - innovation," but in the ability to restructure institutions, open up development space, activate the private sector, attract capital into production, and participate in high value-added stages in the global supply chain.

According to him, for the past 20 years, Vietnam has relied heavily on foreign direct investment (FDI) as a driver of growth, primarily in assembly, processing, and manufacturing on demand, taking advantage of cheap labor and land. This model is suitable for the take-off phase but is insufficient to generate gradually increasing marginal productivity, leading to limitations in development.

From there, the expert emphasized that Vietnam has not yet fallen into the middle-income trap, but the risk is real. This is because the middle-income trap does not occur when a country experiences slow growth, but when growth becomes "untransformed" after the initial industrialization phase. In Southeast Asia, at least four economies have been stuck in this trap for more than a decade.

"Vietnam hasn't fallen into the trap yet, because it hasn't reached the threshold. But if it continues with the current model, the likelihood of falling into the same orbit as Thailand and the Philippines is very high," he observed.

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien, economic expert. Photo: FBNV

Period 2026 - 2030: The final window of transformation

The period from 2026 to 2030 is a "golden" time for Vietnam to overcome the lower-middle-income trap. Besides traditional industries, what are the new breakthrough "driving forces" that will serve as the backbone to help our country become a modern industrialized nation by 2030, sir?

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien : First, we must acknowledge the reality that the timeline of Vietnam's development has two phases: 2026-2030 is the transitional phase for the economic model, and from 2030-2045 is the acceleration and accumulation of competitive capacity. If we lag behind in the first phase, the later phase will only be a continuation of extensive growth with low productivity and a lack of technological capacity.

In fact, the middle-income trap is a situation many countries fall into when growth is based on expanding production and cheap labor but fails to transition to a higher value-added model. In Southeast Asia, about four economies have been in this situation for over a decade and have yet to escape.

Currently, Vietnam remains in the lower-middle income group and has not yet fallen into the "trap," but if it continues to grow at its current momentum, the risk is very high. Vietnam's approach to Thailand's level indicates that the room for extensive growth is gradually running out, and if it doesn't quickly shift its development model, its trajectory will repeat that of countries that came before it.

One of the reasons countries get "stuck" is the FDI attraction model based on outdated technology. Many multinational corporations often move processes that have already depreciated or have not yet recouped their investment to the ASEAN region. This initially leads to rapid growth, but once production infrastructure and labor reach their limits, productivity stops improving, leading to a trap. Vietnam has followed this trajectory in recent times, so the possibility of getting stuck is real.

The achievements, particularly those stemming from the 2025 reforms, have created sufficient momentum and strength for Vietnam to enter the 2026 acceleration phase with a solid foundation and a long-term vision.

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien

We must boldly face the truth: the slogan "developing science and technology" is only meaningful when businesses, as the actual technology-applying entities, have the motivation and conditions to invest. Meanwhile, most countries stuck in this trap have failed to do this because their growth models do not generate endogenous momentum. The difference with Vietnam is that it hasn't fully fallen into the trap yet, so there is still

room for transformation. Countries that fell into the trap earlier have almost filled their industrial space, making restructuring very difficult.

Does that mean that simply chasing the slogan "innovation" won't be enough to create a breakthrough, sir?

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien: For many years, "science and technology" has appeared frequently in resolutions, strategies, and policy forums as one of the pillars determining Vietnam's productivity and long-term growth. However, we must frankly acknowledge that the development of science and technology is just talk. Technology belongs to businesses. Without businesses willing to invest, transformation will not occur.

This is the "blind spot" of the transformation strategy: Vietnam is setting its goals on the technological side, but the tools for implementation lie with businesses, and these two sides haven't really met yet.

In other words, there is currently a mismatch between the goals and the actors: our goals are high technology, high productivity, and high added value, but the actors are businesses. Technology is not enacted by resolutions, nor is it implemented in meeting rooms; it is only realized when businesses decide to invest capital, accept risks, develop products, build markets, and compete.

Foreign customers approach Dony Company to sign garment orders. Photo: Quoc Hai

However, a business only invests in technology when it meets five minimum conditions.

Firstly, the institutional framework is favorable: no delays, no overlaps, and no "approvals based on personal feelings."

Secondly, the market must be large enough: there must be sufficient consumption of technology products, without distortion or being hampered by monopolies.

Thirdly, open development space: including industry space, geographical space, and competitive space.

Fourth, there is the need for cheap capital and capital flow: credit, capital markets, private sector, and FDI must be interconnected, instead of remaining stagnant in land or gold speculation.

Fifth, a crucial condition is the risk-sharing mechanism: businesses benefit from success and don't "die" when they fail. In simpler terms, "benefits must be balanced, and risks must be shared."

Without these five elements, technological innovation becomes a "luxury expense," and slogans remain just slogans.

"Thailand used to be far ahead of Vietnam. But in recent years, Vietnam has caught up. The simple reason is that Vietnam hasn't yet fallen into the trap, so there's still room for growth. If we continue with our current momentum, the chances of falling into the same trap as them are very high."

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien

What suggestions do you have for Vietnam to overcome this "trap"?

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien : The most important solution for Vietnam to avoid falling into the middle-income trap is not to continue attracting FDI using the old model, but to form "national transformation capacity," a concept understood as the state's ability to use institutions and design development space to create new growth opportunities. This capacity is based on three main pillars.

Firstly, there is the institutional framework, which serves as the "infrastructure of growth." Without institutional change, businesses will find it difficult to enter or expand, projects will be implemented slowly, and efficiency will be low.

Secondly, new development space is created through zoning and territorial replanning, forming new urban-industrial corridors. With this new space, Vietnam can prioritize attracting high-tech businesses instead of the outdated FDI flows it experienced previously.

Thirdly, it's about attracting high-value links. Vietnam needs to target stages such as research, design, branding, distribution, and decision-making in the value chain of multinational corporations, instead of just taking on low-value assembly tasks.

Furthermore, Vietnam needs to create new industries and sectors to serve the two major trends of green transformation and digital transformation. Finally, integration policies also need adjustment: maintaining multilateral commitments while proactively pursuing bilateral agreements, and simultaneously building an image of a stable, friendly, open, and neutral Vietnam to attract new capital and technology.

If we continue to attract FDI in the old way, the manufacturing space will soon be filled with low-tech factories, making "upgrading" later on almost impossible. Therefore, the right strategy must be to transition directly to high technology from the outset, instead of repeating the model of ASEAN economies that have gone before us.

If Vietnam can build "national transformation capacity," it can bypass the intermediate stages of the value chain and move directly to the high-value stages.

Activate private sector activity and direct speculative capital into production.

The 2030-2045 targets are not just about GDP figures, but about a qualitative transformation of the economy. So, in your opinion, what are the biggest institutional and human resource bottlenecks that need to be addressed immediately in the next five years to create momentum for a leap forward in labor productivity?

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien: In my opinion, the focus of institutional reform should not be on issuing more resolutions, but on activating the dynamism of the private sector. This is the core point.

History shows that developed countries thrive when property rights and freedom of enterprise are guaranteed, thereby stimulating innovation and wealth accumulation in the private sector. Vietnam has a resolution on private sector development, but it lacks consistency as it simultaneously maintains the view that state-owned enterprises play a dominant role in key industries. This makes policy signals ambiguous.

According to the viewpoint stated, the principle should be: whatever the private sector can do, let the private sector do it; the state should make laws, remove bottlenecks, and provide support; intervention should only occur when the private sector fails to perform the task.

Recent experience has shown that many private corporations have expanded their value chains when opportunities arise, demonstrating a flexibility that the state sector lacks.

Another problem is the lack of synergy mechanisms between the state, private sector, and FDI. Currently, the state controls economic infrastructure, FDI controls production and exports, while the private sector mainly operates in real estate, banking, and services.

This situation does not create a self-reliant industrial base. Therefore, it is necessary to create conditions for private sector participation in production, linking and sharing work with FDI, while the state focuses on creating infrastructure and development space.

The positive aspect is that the orientation towards self-reliance and self-sufficiency has been established in the Party Congress resolution. However, for genuine self-sufficiency, Vietnam needs to master technology in several core industries. If the private sector is capable, then an ecosystem should be created for private sector leadership; if the private sector is not yet capable, then a sufficiently strong state-owned corporation is needed to take on the responsibility. In particular, emphasis should be placed on mastering technology, as this is a factor that not only strengthens economic capacity in peacetime but also supports national defense capabilities in unforeseen circumstances.

Focusing resources on strategic infrastructure, especially the North-South high-speed railway and national data infrastructure, requires enormous capital. So, what is the most effective solution for mobilizing public resources (PPP) so that we not only have modern "hard infrastructure" but also develop a synchronized "soft infrastructure" by 2030, sir?

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien: Vietnam's problem is not a lack of resources, but rather how to activate and direct capital flows. There is a large amount of capital in society, but most of it is tied up in gold, land, or assets that do not serve production purposes. In fact, to implement infrastructure development programs (one of the strategic breakthroughs), the state budget currently only meets less than 20% of the capital needs.

Therefore, mobilizing private capital is essential. However, the private sector will only invest when there is a clear benefit. For PPP projects, the principle that needs to be established is "harmonized benefits - shared risks." Only when this mechanism is operational can private capital be attracted to infrastructure.

Another crucial point is the need to shift social capital from a "holding" state to a "producing" state. This is because the strength of the economy lies not in the amount of capital or resources, but in the speed of money circulation. When capital flows into speculation in gold or land, those assets do not generate goods, services, or jobs. This leaves businesses short of capital to expand production and invest in technology.

In reality, the capital currently held by the people is mainly flowing into gold and land, assets that do not go into production, do not create goods or productivity, leading to a "freezing" of social resources. To redirect capital into production, the state must create

favorable conditions for people to do business, because only when the private economy is stimulated will people invest their assets instead of hoarding them.

Another major bottleneck is the lack of mechanisms to combat speculation, especially in real estate. Allowing large amounts of land to sit idle in the hands of a few individuals leads to high rental prices, a shortage of land for businesses, and a lack of capital flow in the economy. It's clear that this problem cannot be solved completely without taxing speculation. The tax would make hoarded assets more expensive, forcing capital back into productive markets instead of remaining idle in land or gold.

According to him, do we need any 'special' or 'superior' mechanisms to transform institutions from a 'hindrance' into a 'driving force' guiding the economy in the coming period?

Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien: To be honest, the issue of "special mechanisms" for Hanoi or Ho Chi Minh City has been addressed, but its effectiveness has been very limited. The reason is that the granted powers ultimately still have to be implemented according to the current legal system, involving many ministries and agencies. Frankly, giving something away without being able to use it is pointless. Therefore, in my opinion, instead of continuing to request special mechanisms, we need a different approach: enacting an Urban Law, specifically applicable to major growth poles, allowing them to operate under a legal regime appropriate to their urban characteristics.

It's not a specific issue, but the law. And since it's the law, it must be followed, and there will be solutions to any problems. In reality, in my opinion, the bigger bottleneck currently lies in infrastructure investment, where a project is subject to regulation by more than a dozen laws and numerous decrees, each with its own governing body. The consequence is lengthy procedures, significant legal risks, and slow construction progress.

Therefore, I believe that a Law on Infrastructure Investment is urgently needed—a unified legal framework that overrides all other laws within the scope of infrastructure development—so that projects can run seamlessly from planning, land, finance, environment to disbursement.

Because if infrastructure is a breakthrough, then institutions must pave the way for it. Only with a smooth-running infrastructure can social resources be mobilized for the national economy.

Thank you, sir!